

The importance of genres of folklore in the education of preschool children "

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Annotation: organization of activities that enrich children's spiritual image using examples of folk art in the pre-school education organization and wide promotion in practice.

Key words: Proverb, parable, fairy tale, epic, observation, communicative orientation, social situation, emotional experiences, fun games , diction, speech, empathy, dialogue.

One of the most ancient national values of our people is folk art, i.e. folklore art. This art, as a system of artistic traditions, reflects the humanistic ideas of our people and serves to inculcate national and spiritual values related to hope for the future, goodness, kindness, humanity, and patriotism in the minds of future generations. Folklore art is an important resource for deepening children's understanding of the rich national heritage of our people and satisfying their spiritual and moral needs. In the minds of children, the traditional types and genres of folk art are of great importance in the restoration and development of our national values. The system of genres of Uzbek folk oral art based on the art of words is epic, fairy tale, short story, narrative, legend, myth, praise, anecdote, ritual folklore, children's folklore, oral drama, proverb. consists of chants, spells, incantations, applause and cursing. Such artistic heritage is a product of the poetic thinking of our ancestors. Folklore belonging to each genre differs from each other in terms of its own poetic system, performance method, life-household function, attitude to music, artistic reflection of reality, and other aspects. Today, the traditions of high spiritual perfection embodied in folk art are the national basis for educating and bringing up the young generation. That is why it is of practical importance to restore the rich and colorful traditions of the Uzbek folk art, to develop it, to create sufficient opportunities for the realization of the creative potential of the youth today, and to train specialists in folklore and ethnography. The Law "On Education" also stipulates the training of such qualified, intellectually capable, deep spiritual experts necessary for the spiritual life of our country. The national basis of training specialists in the field of folklore and ethnography is to further improve the spiritual values of our people, to deeply inculcate the ideas of the ideology of independence and national values into the minds of the young generation. The reason is that such specialists should contribute to ensuring the continuation of the best traditions of the creative

potential of our ancestors. Folk oral creativity, which artistically interprets the worldview, socio-political, spiritual-aesthetic and philosophical views of our people in its own way, is considered one of the rarest sources of folklore. Folklore works are also valuable because they perfectly reflect the lifestyle, aspirations, customs and ceremonies, traditions of our great ancestors who created the high culture of our people. Folk art is called folklore in science. We all know that the formation of the science of Uzbek folklore began in the 20s of the 20th century. Folklore includes collecting rare examples of folk art, systematizing them, making public and academic publications, and conducting research on folk art. The term "folklore ". In 1846, the English scientist William Toms proposed it. The term "folklore " means "folk wisdom". All art examples created by the people (architecture, painting, jewelry, goldsmithing, music, dance, oral literature) are examples of folklore. That's why experts working in every field of art call their chosen type of activity, the product of creativity "folklore". For example, a musician calls his folk tunes, a choreographer his folk dances, a folklorist scientist calls his folk epics and fairy tales folklore works. In the early times, Uzbek folk oral poetic creation was called "folk literature", "folk literature", "oral literature", "folk oral creativity", and this term was first coined by H. Zarifov (1934 -35 years) began to be used as "Uzbek folklore". Uzbek folk oral poetic creations are examples of spoken word art that includes many genres and artistically reflects the life, history, aspirations, worldviews of ordinary people. , is performed and in the process of performance it is passed from word to word, from generation to generation. Folklore is a syncretic character, combining elements typical of all art forms, in which words, melodies, and certain types of dance are performed in harmony. will be done. Folklore is an artistic reflection of people's life, history, fate. At the heart of folklore works are people's worldviews, concepts from primitive mythological concepts to perfect religious beliefs. A person who has a deep knowledge of the unique features of traditional folklore, a deep understanding of the laws of development of Uzbek folklore in the period of independence, a good understanding of the spiritual needs and scope of interest of the people, who can improve amateur creativity, is full of theoretical and practical aspects of management. training of skilled specialists who mastered it is an urgent issue of today.

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